

Food fraud screening and vulnerability assessment in the olive oil supply chain

Zhijun Wang^{a,*}, Argyro Tsafara^a, Stilianos Arhondakis^b, Athanasia-Maria Dourou^b, Styliani Moraiti^b, Sarah Nolan^a, Nicolò G.M. Cultrera^c, Valentina Passeri^c, Dimitrios Argyropoulos^a

^a School of Biosystems and Food Engineering, University College Dublin, Stillorgan Road, Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland

^b BioCoS PC, Chania 73100, Crete, Greece

^c Institute of Biosciences and Bioresources, National Research Council (CNR), 06128, Perugia, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Olive oil has become a frequent target for food fraud, posing significant influences on the quality and sustainability of the olive oil value chain. To effectively manage and mitigate fraud risks in the olive oil supply chain, this study investigates the overall fraud vulnerability and the differences across its principal tiers: producers, manufacturers, retailers, and external stakeholders. The Food Fraud Vulnerability Assessment (FFVA) tool was applied to evaluate the olive oil fraud vulnerabilities, and a total of 30 fraud factors related to opportunities, motivations, and control measures were examined. A statistical analysis was conducted to assess the number of historical fraud incidents within the olive oil supply chain and to identify the main types of fraud. The frequency of fraud factors was calculated to establish the ranking importance of the three primary fraud categories. Significance analysis was employed to assess differences in key fraud factors across participant roles, while multiple correspondence analysis was used to visualize the distribution pattern of tier groups and their correlation with fraud factor score. Among the three key fraud elements, opportunities showed the highest contribution to vulnerability (41.53 %), followed by motivations (27.10 %) and control measures (14.52 %). Technology opportunity and economic motivation were identified as the main drivers for the olive oil fraud vulnerability assessment. The absence of a fraud prevention system was identified as a critical threat across stakeholders, including producers, manufacturers and retailers. These results provide a comprehensive understanding of fraud dynamic in the olive oil industry, highlighting key drivers, critical points of vulnerability and potential mitigation measures.

1. Introduction

In recent years, with growing public awareness of food safety and healthy lifestyle, the concept of food fraud has become increasingly recognized. The Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme defines food fraud as “any deliberate action of businesses or individuals to deceive others with regard to the integrity of food to gain undue advantage” (Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2018). It involves practices such as diluting high-quality ingredients with low-quality alternatives, misrepresenting the origin or quality of a product, or even selling unsafe, non-food substances as legitimate items (Manning, 2016). In economic research, food fraud can be summarized simply as consumers not getting what they pay for (Charlebois et al., 2016). Unlike

other fraudulent activities, food fraud poses serious public health risks, as adulterated or counterfeited products may contain harmful substances or lack essential nutrients, potentially leading to foodborne illnesses or long-term health complications (Handford et al., 2016). Additionally, food fraud generates substantial economic losses for legitimate producers, distort market prices, and damage the reputation of entire supply chains (Spink et al., 2017). Recent studies have reported that many common, necessary, and expensive food products are easily targeted by food fraudsters (Huisman & Van Ruth, 2022). For instance, honey is often diluted with various sugar syrups, while milk has been found to be adulterated with the addition of water or other protein substitutes (Yang et al., 2020); ground spices such as turmeric and paprika mixed with cheaper plant materials or synthetic dyes (Silvis

* Corresponding author at: University College Dublin, Stillorgan Road, Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland.

E-mail address: michael.wang@nieuwmount.com (Z. Wang).

et al., 2017) and wine has also been reported to be susceptible to dilution or mislabeling of origin Grassi et al. (2024). These cases collectively demonstrate that products with high economic value and low detectability are particularly vulnerable to fraud. Among these, olive oil is one of the most common criminal targets (Fort et al., 2021).

Olive oil plays a central role in many diets due to its rich nutritional profile and health claims. It contains high monounsaturated fats and antioxidants, which benefit heart health and overall well-being (Flori et al., 2019). The olive market size was valued at USD 14.89 billion in 2024, and it is expected to reach USD 18.86 billion by 2029, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.85 % during the forecast period (2024–2029). The European Union (EU) dominates productions, accounting for the largest market (Mili & Bouhaddane, 2021). Olive oil is categorized into Extra Virgin Olive Oil (EVOO), Virgin Olive Oil (VOO), and lower-quality categories. However, as the demand for this premium product grows worldwide, the risk of fraud also increases. Fraudulent practices erode consumer trust and their willingness to pay for high-quality olive oil products. A published meta-analysis of studies on sustainability labels found that consumers were more willing to pay for EVOO labeled as sustainably produced or organic, indicating a preference for transparency and ethical sourcing (Carzedda et al., 2021). Conversely, exposure to olive oil fraud can reduce the perceived value of EVOO up to 50 %, even for premium brands (Meerza & Gustafson, 2019). Adulterated olive oils often exhibit diminished nutritional quality and may pose health risks, such as allergenic reactions when hazelnut oil is used as an adulterant (Ramos-Gómez et al., 2023). EVOO commands a higher market price compared to other types of olive oil as well as to most vegetable oils, making it a prime target for adulteration and mislabeling. Common fraudulent practices include diluting EVOO with lower-quality oils or mispresenting inferior grades as extra virgin olive oil (Guido et al., 2020). Documented cases include dilution of EVOO with lower-grade or non-olive oils, such as soybean or sunflower oil and mislabeling of products as organic or Spanish to exploit Spain's global reputation as a leading producer (JRC Geel, 2024). These practices compromise consumers' confidence and damage the integrity of the olive oil value chain. Socially and environmentally, fraudulent practices in the olive oil supply chain undermine the commercial value of EVOO produced from unique cultivars by traditional communities. In the long-term, this may reduce income and negatively impact the sustainability of olive oil businesses (Carreño & Vergano, 2016). To address the challenges posed by the low detectability of food fraud and its potential impact on supply chain integrity, a range of advanced analytical detection methods has been developed (Pereira et al., 2021). These include Raman Spectrometry (Zou et al., 2009), Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (Maestrello et al., 2022), mass spectrometry (Da Silveira et al., 2017), and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) fingerprints, etc. DNA-based methods are particularly effective in verifying botanical origins of olive oils, especially when adulterants exhibit chemical similarities to EVOO (Piarulli et al., 2019). However, despite these efforts, olive oil fraud remains a significant threat, which means it is crucial to thoroughly understand the characteristics of the olive oil supply chain and establish a comprehensive fraud prevention system.

In the context of food fraud prevention, the above detection challenges are closely connected to the opportunity and detectability elements of fraud vulnerability, as limited analytical capacity increases the likelihood that adulteration may occur without being identified. Therefore, the Food Fraud Vulnerability Assessment (FFVA) tool has been widely applied across supply chains (Manning & Soon, 2019). Food fraud vulnerability refers to deficiencies that, if unaddressed, could pose a threat to consumer health or have adverse economic or reputational consequences. The FFVA is a valuable instrument for identifying weaknesses within the food chain, highlighting risk-prone areas and pinpointing the contributing factors (Van Ruth, 2019). In the past years, FFVA has been applied to diverse supply chains, including milk (Yang et al., 2019, 2020), spices (Silvis et al., 2017), olive oil (Yan et al., 2020), and organic bananas (Van Ruth et al., 2018). Based on these studies, the

vulnerability to fraud is influenced by three primary factors: opportunities, motivations, and control measures, which encompass technical and situational opportunities, economic drivers, cultural and behavioural influences, and both technical and managerial controls (Van Ruth et al., 2017). An inherent strength of a food vulnerability assessment tool is its ability to help supply chain professionals identify potential weaknesses that could be exploited for fraud, thereby supporting of the food supply chain restructuring to proactively prevent fraudulent activities.

In the field of EVOO, fraud is a long-standing and ongoing problem. Recent vulnerability assessments confirm that economically motivated adulteration remains the predominant challenge (Yan et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022). To describe the current status of food fraud dynamics, particularly in EVOO, this study traces global olive oil fraud incidents and incorporates stakeholder perspectives to identify underlying drivers.

This study aims to investigate and analyze potential vulnerabilities and underlying causes of integrity issues in the olive oil supply chain. The history of food fraud incidents is used to identify the most prevalent types of fraud in olive oil. In addition, the frequency of each fraud factor is studied from different stakeholders' perspectives. The relationship between perceived fraud vulnerability, fraud factors, and stakeholder characteristics is explored. The results will provide valuable insights into current types of food fraud, vulnerable nodes, and potential solutions to combat fraud in the olive oil supply chain.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The olive oil supply chain and historical recording of food fraud cases

To clearly present the current state of olive oil fraud data, it is important to understand the basic structure and key participants in the olive oil supply chain. The structure of the olive oil supply chain and participating stakeholders is summarized and illustrated in Fig. 1. The historical datasets of food fraud cases in olive oil were extracted manually from the monthly report published by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in the EU (JRC Geel, 2024). The JRC is the research institution for conducting research, provide independent scientific advice, and to support EU policies with evidence-based findings. As stated by JRC, the media reports of the monthly food fraud report are selected from the Medical Information System (MedISys) and Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) according to selection criteria about the food fraud types, commodities, and fraud definition in the EU.

To obtain the historical recording of the olive oil value chains, a total of 87 JRC monthly reports were scanned from September 2016 to May 2024. There are 57 reports that directly highlight incidents of olive oil fraud. The type of fraud, year, origin country, and description of the incident were extracted from the JRC reports. Fraud types were classified primarily based on the framework proposed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC Geel, 2020). In cases where multiple fraud types were involved, all relevant categories were recorded to reflect the multifaceted nature of the incident. To ensure accuracy, all recordings have undergone secondary manual verification, cross-referenced with the news links provided in the JRC reports.

2.2. The adoption of FFVA for olive oil value chains

In this study, the food fraud vulnerability assessment tool was used to collect information from stakeholders in the olive oil value chains. Briefly, a practical food fraud vulnerability assessment tool was developed previously by SSAFE, which is a nonprofit organization aiming to promote continuous improvement and global recognition of internationally accepted food protection systems and standards through public-private partnerships (Van Ruth et al., 2017). The original FFVA questionnaire was developed for general application across food supply chains. To ensure its suitability for the olive oil sector and to enhance response quality, some items that were not directly related to olive oil

Fig. 1. The basic stages of the olive oil supply chain.

production, processing, or trade were removed. The core structure of the FFVA, comprising the three domains of opportunity, motivation, and control measures, was fully retained. The adapted questionnaire captures the specific characteristics of the olive oil supply chain while maintaining methodological consistency with the standardized FFVA framework. The complete version of the adapted questionnaire is provided in the Supplementary Material (Table S1). The adopted questionnaire contains 30 questions covering three category elements, each question related to the identified fraud factors: 8 for opportunities, 10 for motivations, and 12 for control measures (Table 1). The opportunities section contains indicators related to product and process characteristics, features of the industry network, and historical evidence of fraud associated with specific food products and ingredients. The motivations section includes indicators for organizational aspects such as business culture, historical offenses, and economic conditions of the company, suppliers, and customers. The control measures section comprises mitigation and contingency control indicators. Three descriptions are provided for each opportunity and motivation indicator, reflecting three risk levels (low, moderate, and high). Similarly, for each control indicator, three descriptions are provided to reflect the level of control. Each indicator should select a description that accurately reflects the company's situation. Then, the updated questionnaires were

Table 1

The key elements in food fraud vulnerability assessment and 30 related fraud factors included in the adopted FFVA questionnaire.

Key elements	Fraud factors
Opportunities	1. Complexity of adulteration raw materials
	2. Availability of technology and knowledge to adulterate raw materials
	3. Detectability adulteration raw materials
	4. Availability of technology and knowledge to adulterate final products
	5. Detectability adulteration final products
	6. Complexity of counterfeiting
	7. Detectability of counterfeiting
	8. Transparency chain network
Motivation	9. Supply and pricing raw materials
	10. Valuable components or attributes raw materials
	11. Economic conditions own company
	12. Organizational strategy own company
	13. Financial strains supplier
	14. Economic conditions supplier
	15. Economic conditions branch of industry
	16. Ethical business culture branch of industry
	17. Level of competition branch of industry
	18. Price asymmetries
Control	19. Fraud monitoring system raw materials
	20. Verification of fraud mon. system raw materials
	21. Fraud monitoring system final products
	22. Verification of fraud monitoring system final products
	23. Information system own company
	24. Tracking and tracing system own company
	25. Contractual require suppliers
	26. Tracking and tracing system supplier
	27. Social control chain network
	28. Fraud control industry
	29. National food policy
	30. Contingency

used in the workshop with stakeholders from different food supply chains. The feedback from the stakeholders and the following analysis will indicate the potential food fraud risk factors and mitigation measures that determine the actual fraud vulnerability.

2.3. Data collection

Data were collected using the FFVA tool through both in-person and online workshops involving 31 stakeholders of the olive oil value chain. As summarized in Table S2 of the supplementary materials, 12 participants were from Greece, including 10 producers, one manufacturer, and one external stakeholder; 14 participants were from Italy, comprising five producers, two retailers, and seven external stakeholders. An additional five participants came from other countries, including the United Kingdom, Switzerland, and Germany, contributing three retailers and two manufacturers. Based on their role within the olive oil supply chain, participants were divided into four-tier groups, including 15 olive oil producers, three manufacturers, five retailers and eight external stakeholders. External stakeholders are defined as non-direct actors in the supply chain. While they are not involved in producing, processing, and selling olive oil, they carry out essential tasks such as laboratory testing and product certification.

Among all the questionnaires received, 23 were collected during in-person workshops and 8 were completed online. Both groups of participants used the same questionnaire. Regardless of whether the survey was administered online or in person, assistance and clarification were provided through direct support or online meetings. During the workshop, each participant received an information sheet and consent form prior to the session, followed by detailed instructions to ensure proper completion of the questionnaire. After the workshops, participants' answers were collected for the data analysis. In the online survey, participants were first required to complete an informed consent form and read the introduction to the questionnaire. Throughout the process, timely support and clarification were available via online meetings. A total of 31 completed questionnaires were collected and used for the food fraud vulnerability assessment in the olive oil supply chain.

2.4. Data analysis

2.4.1. The frequency of food fraud vulnerability

A three-level scoring system was applied to analyze the FFVA results. For the food fraud factors related to the section opportunities and motivations, a score of 1, 2, or 3 correspond to low, medium, and high vulnerability, respectively. Conversely, for the fraud factors related to the control measures, scores of 1, 2, or 3 indicate high, medium, and low vulnerability. The food fraud vulnerability frequencies were calculated as the percentages of low, medium, and high vulnerability scores for each fraud factor and tier group. Overall, the responses reflect the general fraud situation within the olive oil value chain, while the tier group results allow for comparison of stakeholders' roles influence their level of vulnerability to food fraud.

The frequency of perceived vulnerability levels for each key element is determined using the following formula:

$$F_i = \frac{S_{ij}}{G_j} \quad (1)$$

The F_i is the frequency of the vulnerability score i ($i = 1, 2, 3$), S_{ij} is the number of observations that get score i in the following group j (j means the key elements of food fraud vulnerability), G_j is the total number of observations in groups (Yan et al., 2020). The scales in the Control section run in opposite directions due to the specific design of the questions in this part. The questions are structured to assess whether participants have adequate measures to prevent fraud, thus necessitating a reversal in the scale compared to those used for opportunity and motivation. This reversal not only aligns to measure control effectiveness but also facilitates statistical convenience in the analysis. All calculations were performed using R software (version 4.3; R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

2.4.2. Univariate analysis

Non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis tests were used for group comparisons due to the ordinal nature of the data in this study (Yan et al., 2020). Statistical significance was determined by comparing the observed test statistic (H) against its chi-square distribution with the corresponding degrees of freedom. When overall significance was detected, pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests were conducted for post-hoc comparisons, with significance levels computed based on the standardized U statistic and its corresponding p-value. Mean ranks were utilized to assess the perceived fraud vulnerability of different factors across groups. A higher mean rank indicates a greater perceived vulnerability to fraud. All data analysis was performed using R 4.3 software (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

2.4.3. Cluster analysis

In this study, multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) was employed to investigate the associations among various groups. This statistical method effectively highlights the relationships between two categorical variables using data derived from a contingency table. MCA is an extension of this technique, permitting the summary and visualization of data encompassing more than two categorical variables, thereby enhancing our understanding of complex interrelationships. The analysis identified the influence of stakeholders' roles and various fraud factors based on the results obtained from the MCA. The analysis and related visual representations were conducted using R 4.3 software (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The olive oil supply chain

Understanding the status of the olive oil supply chain is essential before addressing the issue of food fraud vulnerability. As highlighted in previous research, the olive oil supply chain is a complex network encompassing multiple stages, from cultivation to final consumption, and involving several stakeholders. The main production regions are still concentrated in Mediterranean countries such as Greece, Italy, and Spain, although other countries, including Turkey, and Morocco, are gaining ground due to investments in the industry. These countries benefit from favorable climatic conditions, long-standing agricultural traditions, and well-established processing infrastructures. The principal markets for olive oil are Europe and North America, with Asia emerging as a rapidly growing destination due to rising consumer awareness of its health benefits. However, this expanding global demand also increased the susceptibility of the olive oil supply chain to food fraud, which can occur at any stage.

The basic structure of the olive oil supply chain consists of several key stakeholders, each playing a crucial role in maintaining the quality and integrity of the product. As shown in Fig. 1, the chain comprises five generic stages: Field, Mill, Storage, Bottling, and Retailer. Based on some

published articles, participants can be categorized into three groups: producers, manufacturers, and retailers. The producers, including small-scale farmers and large agricultural enterprises, are responsible for cultivating and harvesting olives at optimal ripeness. Manufacturers process the olives into oil, using methods such as cold pressing to preserve the oil's chemical properties and flavor. Retailers distribute olive oil to consumers, often through supermarkets, dedicated stores, and online platforms. At the same time, olive oil has relatively systematic laboratory analysis, certification agencies, associations, etc. Although not directly involved in production and sales, these actors possess extensive knowledge of the olive oil supply chain. For example, certification agencies and regulatory bodies play a critical role in ensuring compliance with standards, monitoring the authenticity of products, and granting designations such as "extra virgin". To more comprehensively evaluate the views of all participants in olive oil, we classify the above organizations as external stakeholders. Each stakeholder is interconnected, and the smooth functioning of the supply chain depends on robust coordination, transparency, and enforcement of regulations. To mitigate fraud risks in olive oil production, the hidden driving factors should be assessed using the food fraud vulnerability tool, thereby protecting both consumers and ethical stakeholders within the industry.

3.2. The historical recording of food fraud in olive oil supply chains

In this paper, the classification and description of fraud types follow the framework outlined by the European Commission. Briefly, there are seven main food fraud types. Among them, the dilution involves mixing a high-value liquid ingredient with one of lower value. Substitution refers to replacing an ingredient or part of a high-value product with one of lesser value. Concealment entails hiding the low quality of certain food ingredients or products. Mislabeling involves making false claims on packaging to achieve economic gain. Unapproved enhancement includes adding undeclared materials to food products to improve quality attributes. Counterfeiting entails imitating legitimate products, such as brand name, packaging, recipes, or processing methods, for profit. Finally, grey market production, theft, and diversion refer to selling excess or unreported products. For the olive oil supply chain, the details of fraud cases and types were summarized in the following sections.

Figs. 2 and 3 illustrate the annual and country-level distribution of fraud cases and fraud types in the olive oil supply chain between September 2016 and May 2024. Notably, the total number of olive oil fraud types recorded (134) exceeds the number of fraud incidents (96). This discrepancy arises because a single case often involves multiple fraud type. This implies that one incident committed on a specific date included, for example, both the mix of extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) with lower-grade olive oil (substitution) and the use of false claims on packaging (mislabeling). As shown in Fig. 2, olive oil fraud cases are reported annually in the media and included in the JRC's monthly food fraud summary report. The data reveal an upward trend, with >10 cases in 2022 and 2023, and 13 cases in the first five months of 2024. The increasing number of olive oil fraud cases could be caused by the rise in global consumption. Global consumption reached approximately 2970,000 metric tonnes in 2019/2020, and the increase in demand has driven a significant rise in olive oil prices. As a result, the high economic value of olive oil creates strong financial motivations for fraud within the supply chain Nasr et al. (2022). These statistical conclusions are consistent with the views of many food fraud reviews, that the problem of food fraud in olive oil has become very common and needs to be taken seriously by producers, sellers, consumers, and regulatory authorities (Casadei et al., 2021; Conte et al., 2020; Visciano & Schirone, 2021). JRC data further highlight that Italy, Brazil, and Spain are frequently cited in fraud incidents, likely due to their dual role in both production and processing (Crizel et al., 2020; Mattas et al., 2020).

As shown in Fig. 4, mislabeling emerges as the most common type of fraud in the olive oil industry, according for 50 % of cases. In addition to mislabeling, recent JRC data indicate that dilution represents about 12

Fig. 2. The number of fraud cases compared to the number of fraud types annually from September 2016 until May 2024.

Fig. 3. The total number of fraud cases and fraud types per country in the olive oil supply chain from September 2016 until May 2024.

% of incidents, substitution approximately 14 %, and grey-market activities around 18 %. Most fraudulent practices appear to occur after milling, possibly in the middle of the supply chain, such as at the packaging unit. This finding is consistent with the statistical trend of olive oil fraud cases previously shown in Fig. 4b, indicating that mislabeling is the most frequent among other fraud types in that particular year 2023. Mislabeling was the dominant fraud type in every year analyzed, and in the first five months of 2024 alone, 13 fraud cases were reported, involving 19 distinct fraud types. This number may increase as more reports are published throughout the year.

3.3. The perceived fraud vulnerability in the olive oil supply chains

3.3.1. The overall fraud vulnerability results

The food fraud vulnerability results in each factor and tier groups are discussed across three main sections: opportunities, motivations, and control measures. Fig. 5 provides an overall visualization of the relative frequencies of vulnerability scores. In this representation, green color low vulnerability, orange to a medium, and red to a high. A predominance of red and orange colors highlights greater perceived vulnerability. In detail, questions 1–8 correspond to the opportunity section, questions 9–18 to motivation, and questions 19–30 to control measures.

The results show that most of fraud factors are marked orange and red, which means that the participants overall perceive most fraud factors as medium to high vulnerability. This interpretation suggests that there are many potential vulnerabilities in the olive oil supply chain that can be exploited by counterfeiters, leading to fraud incidents. This is further supported by the large (or increased) number of such incidents reported in recent years related to olive oil (Guido et al., 2020).

To capture the overall situation in three main sections, the food fraud vulnerability frequencies of opportunities, motivation, and control are shown in Fig. 6. Only 23.76 % of all fraud factors were rated as low vulnerability (green), while medium to high vulnerability (orange and red), dominated the results. Within the opportunities section, 41.53 % of factors were rated as high vulnerability. In the motivation section, 50.65 % of factors were perceived as medium risk, with an additional 27.10 % rated as high-risk, indicating significant vulnerability in this dimension. Although more than half of the fraud factors in the control section were considered medium risk, most of the factors related to the food fraud prevention system, such as Q19 (Fraud monitoring system raw materials), Q21 (Fraud monitoring system final products), and Q28 (Fraud control industry) were identified as high-risk fraud factors.

In summation, these findings indicate that the vulnerability of olive oil to fraud falls to high-risk level. Among the three main fraud elements,

Fig. 4. The overview of food fraud types in olive oil supply chains. (a) The predominant food fraud types in the olive oil supply chain; (b) The reported numbers of food fraud cases based on different fraud types from September 2016 until May 2024.

Fig. 5. The relative frequencies of vulnerability scores of fraud factors from all respondents for the 30 fraud factors. The portions of low, medium, and high vulnerability are colored green, orange, and red, respectively.

opportunities scored the highest scores (41.53 %), followed by motivations (27.10 %) and control measures (14.52 %). Correspondingly,

Fig. 5 indicates that the main fraud drivers and enablers factors are: Q1-Complexity of adulteration raw materials, Q2-Availability technology

Fig. 6. The low-medium-high food fraud vulnerability frequencies in the olive oil supply chains for the three key elements: opportunities, motivations, and control measures. The portions of low, medium, and high vulnerability are colored green, orange, and red, respectively.

and knowledge to adulterate raw materials, Q3-Detectability adulteration raw materials, Q4-Availability technology, and knowledge to adulterate final products, Q5-Detectability adulteration final products, Q7-Detectability of counterfeiting, Q9-Supply and pricing raw materials, Q10- Valuable components or attributes raw materials, Q17-Level of competition branch of industry Q18- Price asymmetries.

The findings on opportunity, motivation, and control measures in this study align closely with patterns reported in the EU JRC monthly fraud reports (Fig. 4). For example, mislabeling remains the most frequently detected fraud type in the olive oil sector, accounting for approximately 50 % of olive-oil-related alerts in recent JRC datasets. This pattern is strongly associated with economic motivations, as mislabeling of origin or quality can yield significant financial gains within the olive oil supply chain. In addition, substitution and dilution account for about 14 % and 12 % of reported cases (Fig. 4), respectively, and are often driven by the simplicity of adulteration methods and the limited availability of effective detection capabilities within stakeholders.

3.3.2. Opportunities

In food fraud vulnerability assessment, "Opportunity" denotes the conditions that facilitate the potential for fraudulent acts within the food supply chain. This concept encompasses the gaps between the physical and chemical properties of food, production line management, and adulteration technology. Specifically, 41.53 % of opportunity-related factors were classified as high vulnerability, 40.73 % as medium vulnerability, and only 17.74 % as low vulnerability (Fig. 6). Such vulnerabilities enable actors to adulterate or misrepresent products with low risk of detection. The bar chart of opportunities-related frequencies (Fig. 6) shows that the availability of technology and knowledge to adulterate final products (Q4) and detectability of adulteration final products (Q5) were rated as high-level fraud risks and thus were considered to contribute more to average fraud vulnerability in opportunity section. Similar to other vegetable oils, the liquid nature and visual appearance of olive oil make it particularly susceptible to adulteration. In addition to Q4 and Q5, most of the fraud factors in olive oil opportunity section were marked orange-red, indicating that adulteration present few technical Challenges. Given its liquid state, olive oil can be easily substituted or adulterated.

The results obtained in the opportunity section of the food fraud vulnerability assessment can be confirmed by the main types of olive oil adulteration reported by the EU. Namely, substitution and dilution can easily occur throughout the olive oil supply chain from production to sales (Fig. 4). As reported in other liquid food products such as milk and

edible vegetable oil, the low technical difficulty of adulteration is a key driven of high fraud vulnerability from a technology perspective (Yang et al., 2020, 2022). The results of this study are consistent with the finding that oil products are easily be substituted by lower-quality ones (De Lima et al., 2020). At the same time, it is very easy for low-quality olive oil to be used to impersonate or adulterate high-quality EVOO during production. This vulnerability is reflected in some factors such as the low complexity of counterfeiting (Q6) and not detectability of counterfeiting (Q7). Overall, these results demonstrate that adulterating olive oil, including high-end EVOO, is technically simple, while detecting such fraud remains difficult and costly.

3.3.3. Motivations

Alongside opportunities, the motivation section is another major driver of food fraud in the olive oil supply chain. >70 % of motivation-related fraud factors were rated as medium to high fraud vulnerability (Fig. 6). This section examines the impact of economic factors on food fraud, such as price differences based on origins, market competition, and corporate culture. Previous studies have shown that internal economic factors (e.g. management strategy, product prices) and external industry competition can significantly motivate stakeholders to commit fraud for financial gain Huisman and Van Ruth, (2022). The vulnerability assessment results revealed that several fraud factors, such as the valuable components or attributes raw materials (Q10), the level of industry competition (Q11), and price asymmetries (Q18), were marked red, indicating high-level vulnerability (Fig. 5). It was reported that consumers are more inclined to purchase olive oil with attractive colors and flavors, which can motivate fraudulent practices in the olive oil value chains (Yan et al., 2020). Similarly, Dekhili et al. (2011) found that consumers often associate olive oil quality with sensory cues such as "Extra virgin" mention, colour, and appearance. This explains why Q10 was rated as high risks: adulterated EVOO could attract more consumers and generate higher profits. Nutritional research further supports this, showing that EVOO is rich in unsaturated fatty acids and antioxidants, which makes consumers willing to pay premium prices (Handford et al., 2016).

In addition to the nutritional quality of olive oil, the present result also found that price differences caused by production origins are also an important motivation for fraud. For example, the factor price asymmetries (Q18) were marked red as high-level vulnerability. Since olive oil quality is closely related to climate and farm management at its origin Ballco and Gracia, (2020), consumers often develop strong preferences for brands associated with prestigious origin labels. According to a

recent study labeling attention significantly influences consumers' choices when it comes to olive oil (Sgroi et al., 2024). This purchasing psychology leads to higher prices for olive oil from well-known origins, and food counterfeiters often tamper with the origin of labels to obtain illegal profits. Research has shown that mislabeling origins or organic certification can greatly increase illegal profits (Maritano et al., 2024). Historical data also indicated that mislabeling is the most frequently reported type of olive oil fraud (JRC Geel, 2020). At the same time, recent food fraud vulnerability research has pointed out that cultural and behavioral drivers also play an important role in food fraud in commodities. Take the dairy supply chains as an example, the increasing international competition may force small-scale producers to engage in adulteration to maintain profits (Yang et al., 2019). In the present study of olive oil, it has been reported that the supply chain is very competitive in terms of product price (Bimbo et al., 2019). Therefore, it could be expected that the higher level of competition in the industry (Q17) could lead to higher frequency of fraud vulnerability. The findings reveal that the olive oil industry is characterized by intense competition, which may serve as a significant catalyst for food fraud.

3.3.4. Control measures

Overall, the situation in the control measures was improved compared with the sections on opportunities and motivations. The vulnerability of food fraud in control measures is generally less than the opportunity and motivation. Fig. 6 showed that only 14.52 % of fraud factors were rated as high vulnerability. However, since many participants assigned medium-level rating to most food fraud factors and given that the lack of control systems is often related to regulatory gaps, it is reasonable to infer that the risk assessment of food vulnerability in terms of control measures is underestimated. Companies are often reluctant to disclose their weaknesses to regulators, treating these fraud factors as private or sensitive, and may therefore provide answers that appear more secure. This would be in agreement with psychological research on questionnaires, which shows that respondents are likely to reduce their expression of serious situations when faced with sensitive topics (Tourangeau & Yan, 2007). Considering that regulatory authorities currently only have strong supervision of food safety, the focus that deserves improvement is still a reliable food fraud prevention system.

According to survey participants, a large amount of olive oil is processed and produced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Due to their limited scale, these enterprises are limited by scale and do not have the financial capacity or resources to invest in modern, complex traceability systems or to conduct regular controls. Consequently, guidance from regulatory authorities and the development of affordable traceability system have become extremely important (Conti, 2022). Over 30 % of the participants lacked of fraud monitoring system for raw materials (Q19) and a track and trace system of the company (Q20), both factors were assessed as medium to high vulnerability.

Other fraud factors, including Fraud monitoring system final products (Q21), Contractual requirements for suppliers (Q25), Tracking and tracing system supplier (Q26), and Contingency (Q30), were mainly marked as orange and red in Fig. 5. The lack of necessary food fraud control systems has been reported in other supply chains, such as dairy (Yang et al., 2019), spice (Silvis et al., 2017), and cocoa (Van Ruth et al., 2018). This may be due to the lack of legal control measures, because the regulatory system directly related to food fraud is lacking in most countries, especially compared with the food safety regulatory systems, such as the hazard analysis critical control point (HACCP) system (Tunalioglu et al., 2012). This finding reveals that the absence of a universal and trustworthy fraud control system is a key factor that contributes significantly to the current fraud in the olive oil industry. It is crucial to have a systematic fraud detection system to better safeguard the integrity of the supply chain in practical applications.

3.4. Differences in food fraud vulnerability between tier groups

3.4.1. Cluster analysis in perceived fraud vulnerability patterns for supply chains

An overview of the MCA for the fraud vulnerability of producers, manufacturers, retailers, and external stakeholders is presented in Fig. 7. The analysis highlights the relationships between variables (scores of fraud factors) and categories (tier groups), with the first two dimensions explain a total variance of 28.40 %. In general, the producer group is widely distributed and overlaps with the external stakeholders. However, the manufacturers and retailers' groups are more distinct. The MCA individual plot (Fig. 7a) illustrates the clusters of stakeholder roles, while the variables plot (Fig. 7b) reflects differences in the stakeholders distribution based on fraud factor score.

The manufacturer group is separated on the left side along F1 from other tier groups in Fig. 7a. The potential reason is that the manufacturer shows relatively low scores for opportunities, as shown in Fig. 7b. The scores in fraud factors, including Q1, Q2, and Q3, contribute to this separation. However, the contribution of motivation is mainly found in the retailer group, which is located on the upside along the F2 from manufacturers and retailers but overlapping slide with producer groups. Such separation is driven by the different scores of retailer participants at fraud factors in the motivation section, such as Q10, Q15, Q16, Q17, and Q18, compared with other groups. It is noted that the location of retailer groups is strongly driven by the results of motivation than other tier groups (Fig. 7b), which indicates that retailers are generally more vulnerable to fraud than the other tier groups and they are perceived as more likely to be victims of fraud. The results align with the previous study reporting that retailers of vegetable oil supply chains suffer fraud more frequently than producers due to economic motivations (Yang et al., 2022).

These findings indicate that the assignment to the clusters is highly associated with the role of stakeholders in the supply chains, the same trends are also reported in the milk and vegetable oil supply chains. The combination effects of opportunity, motivation, and controls played an important role in determining the cluster analysis. The producer is close to the effects of opportunities and control, but the retailers and manufacturers are more vulnerable to food fraud due to the effects of the motivations.

3.4.2. The frequency differences in relevant fraud factors

The survey revealed that perceived fraud vulnerability in olive oil supply chains varied across tier groups with medium to high vulnerability prevalent among the four practitioner roles involved. Producers were identified as having the highest level of vulnerability, scoring 31.11 % (Fig. 8), which may be attributed to the small scale of production and insufficient control measures. External stakeholders reported over 60 % of fraud factors as medium risk and >20 % as high risk. Despite differences in self-assessment, the overall vulnerability of olive oil remains classified as medium to high risk, consistent with findings for other food commodities (Van Ruth et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022).

Opportunities. The overall frequency of medium and high vulnerability in opportunities by the four different tier groups was higher than 50 %. It indicated that the food fraud vulnerability nodes in the opportunity section are assigned to medium-high risk among all the tier groups. There are also several differences in details. Manufacturers showed the highest vulnerability in opportunity than all the other three groups, which could be explained by their high scores in fraud factors because the manufacturers have the most access to the production line, and the adulteration opportunity is higher than producers and retailers. The olive oil supply chain was described by several published papers that lack transparency, with many of the food fraud cases exposed occurring during the processing stage. Consequently, in terms of the results in the opportunity section, the manufacturers are generally more vulnerable to committing fraud. Furthermore, they are perceived as

Fig. 7. MCA plotting to show the effects of stakeholders' role in the food fraud vulnerability (a) Individuals plot (b) variables plot. The numbers of the variables refer to question number about the food fraud factors.

Fig. 8. The frequency differences in fraud sections between tier groups. (a) Producer, (b) Manufacturer, (c) Retailer, (d) External stakeholders. The portions of low, medium, and high vulnerability are colored green, orange, and red, respectively.

more likely to be victims of fraud due to the increased opportunities in performing fraud (adulteration) in the olive oil industry, since it does not require complex technologies or expertise (knowledge).

Motivations. The frequency of high risk in the area of economic motivation is ranked from highest to lowest as follows: retailers, producers, and manufacturers. Retailers reported medium to high vulnerability scores exceeding 80 %, suggesting strong susceptibility to economic interests (Everstine et al., 2013). Producers showed similar trends, influenced by upstream suppliers pricing and consumer purchasing power, leaving them particularly vulnerable to factors such as company economic conditions (Q11), financial strains on suppliers (Q13), and industry competition (Q17). These findings align with a study that reported economically motivated adulteration (EMA) as a significant issue within food supply chains. The results reveal imbalanced interaction among different tier groups concerning economic motivation. As a result, retailers and producers were assigned high vulnerability scores to the fraud factors related to motivation.

Control measures. Most of the producers, manufacturers, retailers, and external stakeholders stated that the olive oil fraud vulnerability level is medium (orange around 50 %). Producers showed the highest vulnerability (22.22 %), primary due to the absence of fraud monitoring system, tracking and tracing mechanisms, and contingency plans. This issue may arise because most olive oil producers are small to medium-sized. As a result, it can be challenging to implement a high-tech and expensive professional traceability system due to its limited production scale. This finding aligns with research on the dairy supply chain, which indicates that small-scale farms often struggle with reliable technical management and effective traceability systems (Yang et al., 2019). Food processing plants, like the manufacturers in the olive oil supply chain, often employ well-trained staff for quality control and have the resources and equipment for food traceability systems (Soon et al., 2019). Fig. 8 illustrates that manufacturers generally perceive themselves as having stronger control measures, with only 2.75 % of fraud factors marked as high risk, a stark contrast to their assessment of opportunities. Therefore, the olive oil manufacturers (green = 61.11 %) have more adequate control measures in place, but the producers are more vulnerable to food fraud.

3.4.3. Statistical evaluation of the effects of role on perceived fraud vulnerability

To assess the significance of the differences between the 4 tier groups, the mean rank of the tier groups for each factor was calculated. Higher ranks in opportunity, motivation, and control factors indicate greater vulnerability. The differences in factor scores between groups were examined for their significance to reveal the influence of the stakeholder's role. Overall, nine fraud factors revealing significant differences (Mann-Whitney U test, $p < 0.05$) as presented in Table 2. These included three motivation-related fraud factors (Q12, Q13, Q16) and five control-related factors (Q19, Q20, Q24, Q25, Q26, Q28). For example, retailers demonstrated less confidence in their suppliers compared with other groups in relation to fraud factor Q24 (Tracking and tracing system own company). This is in line with the reality of food

supply chain because the retailers cannot directly participate in the production control of raw materials and quality inspection of products. The previously published paper similarly reported that external fraud occurred more frequently for the role of retailers in general food supply chains (Manning, 2016).

In the motivation section, producers demonstrated significant vulnerability due to economic pressures both within and outside the company (Q12, Q13 and Q16) than the other tier groups. Specifically, the fraud factor, financial strains supplier (Q13), were highly related to the stress from the whole supply chain, which indicates that the producers are more easily influenced by economic motivations. This finding is consistent with a more basic theory in economics is that producers, especially farmers, may be more sensitive to price fluctuations in the supply chain, which may lead to fraud in order to maintain profits (Van Ruth et al., 2018). External stakeholders play a unique role in the olive oil supply chain. They are responsible for quality testing and providing services such as origin certification. Although they are not direct producers or sellers, their perspective on food fraud in the olive oil supply chain is also important. Significant differences (Mann-Whitney U test, $p < 0.05$) between external stakeholders and other participants are presented in the fraud factors such as financial strains supplier (Q13), fraud monitoring system raw materials (Q19), verification of fraud monitor system raw materials (Q20), and tracking and tracing system own company (Q24). The results showed more significant differences from the perspective of external stakeholders, indicating that certification and lab analysis bodies are more concerned about the traceability system of raw materials and final products, and they generally believe that the olive oil supply chain is vulnerable to economically driven adulteration and that internal control systems need to be strengthened. Based on the tier-specific vulnerability patterns identified in this study, it is necessary to strengthen targeted mitigation measures across different stakeholder groups. For instance, producers can improve upstream control by adopting supplier verification templates and authentication protocols. Retailers may enhance product integrity through contractual requirements for routine authenticity testing. Certification bodies can contribute by providing standardized guidance on sampling and analytical procedures. These measures offer practical strategies aligned with the roles and responsibilities of each tier in the olive oil supply chain.

4. Conclusions

The findings of this study indicate that the olive oil supply chain faces significant challenges related to high vulnerability to food fraud. The assessment of opportunity, motivation, and control measures helps further elucidate the underlying drivers of this vulnerability. This vulnerability stems from various factors unique to the industry and its stakeholders. Overall, the assessment results of fraud vulnerability indicated that the opportunity is the most vulnerable section due to the combined result of the liquid nature of olive oil (easy to admix) and the no need for complex and high-cost adulteration technologies. The vulnerability of different tier groups was further assessed through

Table 2

Mean ranks of scores of the fraud factors from the food fraud vulnerability assessments for the tier groups, and the statistical relevance of differences.

Question number	Fraud factors	Producer (n = 12)	Manufacturer (n = 3)	Retailer (n = 5)	External stakeholder (n = 8)
Q12	Organizational strategy own company	16.80 ^{ab}	8.50 ^b	11.20 ^b	20.31 ^a
Q13	Financial strains supplier	13.16 ^b	8.00 ^b	20.40 ^{ab}	21.56 ^a
Q16	Ethical business culture branch of industry	17.37 ^a	7.17 ^b	16.40 ^a	16.50 ^a
Q19	Fraud monitoring system raw materials	16.20 ^a	6.50 ^b	13.60 ^a	20.68 ^a
Q20	Verification of fraud mon. system raw materials	15.73 ^{ab}	7.00 ^b	14.00 ^{ab}	21.25 ^a
Q24	Tracking and tracing system own company	18.07 ^a	14.66 ^{ab}	7.90 ^b	17.68 ^a
Q25	Contractual require suppliers	19.43 ^a	8.00 ^b	11.67 ^{ab}	15.31 ^{ab}
Q26	Tracking and tracing system supplier	19.00 ^a	18.00 ^b	10.60 ^b	13.00 ^b
Q28	Fraud control industry	17.90 ^a	6.00 ^b	16.10 ^a	16.12 ^a

a-b, the different superscripts indicate the significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

statistical analysis. Compared with the manufacturers, the producer group exhibited significant differences in the critical fraud factors, such as the economic conditions of the company and the ethical business culture branch of the industry. In the MCA cluster analysis, the producers, manufacturers, retailers, and external stakeholders exhibit distinct patterns, influenced by their specific scores in relative fraud factors according to their roles within the supply chain. While there are similarities in motivational vulnerabilities among these groups, significant differences exist in terms of the stakeholders' role. The retailers are more vulnerable under the economic motivations, and for the producers, the main vulnerable nodes were reported in the control section. To tackle these vulnerabilities, olive oil stakeholders are encouraged to develop systematic fraud prevention systems and invest in testing technologies, while also tailoring strategies to address the specific risks linked to their role in the supply chain. To address the specific challenges posed by food fraud in the olive oil supply chain, the adoption of advanced technological solutions is becoming increasingly important. Rapid spectroscopic screening, blockchain-enabled traceability, and digital authentication platforms can enhance detection capabilities and improve transparency across different stages of the supply chain. Furthermore, closer alignment with global policy frameworks, such as JRC monitoring systems and internationally harmonized standards, can strengthen regulatory coordination and support more effective fraud mitigation. It is recommended to develop a comprehensive food fraud prevention framework that incorporates advanced food control measures and real-time detection technologies. Such an integrated system would enhance supply chain traceability, strengthen fraud mitigation strategies, ensure product authenticity, and ultimately reinforce consumer trust. In addition, the relatively small sample size represents a limitation of this study and may restrict the external validity of the findings. Future studies should aim to strengthen representativeness by expanding participant recruitment across additional regions and stakeholder groups.

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Ethical statement

All ethical procedures were followed within the framework of the Watson project and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zhijun Wang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Argyro Tsafara:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stilianos Arhondakis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Athanasia-Maria Dourou:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Styliani Moraiti:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sarah Nolan:** Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Nicolò G.M. Cultrera:** Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Valentina Passeri:** Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dimitrios Argyropoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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